

SELF-DETERMINATION, QUALITY OF COACHING AND COUNTER-PRODUCTIVE USE OF TECHNOLOGY AS CRITICAL FACTORS OF ECE PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' READINESS TO TEACH

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ABSTRACT

Education programs prepare preservice teachers to teach. The readiness of preservice teachers to teach is characterized with self-determination, quality of coaching and counterproductive use of technology. This study aimed to determine if these critical factors affect the readiness of preservice teachers to teach. This study investigated the significant influence of these critical factors to the teaching readiness of 120 ECE preservice teachers. It employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Modified instruments were used, content validated, and pilot tested. Descriptive statistics were used to describe self-determination, quality of coaching, counterproductive use of technology, and preservice teachers' readiness to teach. Meanwhile, multiple linear regression was used to determine the significant influence of the predictor variables on their readiness to teach. The results show high degree of self-determination and quality of coaching which implies that ECE preservice teachers feel competent, self-assured, and independent, and that they received highly effective quality of coaching that helped them in their teaching career. Counterproductive use of technology shows moderate result signifying that it does not severely affect the respondent's readiness to teach. Results also shows that high level of readiness to teach among the participants was significantly influence by self-determination and quality of coaching. Hence, these are key factors that help preservice teachers prepare for the teaching profession. By integrating insights from educational studies, this study provides evidence-based recommendations for school administrator and ECE teachers to develop intuitive coaching initiatives that will help promote and develop preservice teachers' motivation and self-determination, and their teaching skills.

Keywords: *Self-determination, Quality of Coaching, Counter-productive Use of Technology*

INTRODUCTION

Education courses equip education students with necessary strategies, knowledge, and understanding of the teaching and learning process. Teachers, who have an important role in schools, must meet various educational standards, including pedagogical, professional, personality, and social norms (Girgin and Akcanca, 2021). This shows how important it is for future learners to achieve academic success by exposing them to trained, qualified, qualified and devoted teachers (Kristiawan & Puspita, 2021). Readiness to teach refers to the pre-service teachers' preparedness and competence to assume their teaching responsibilities effectively. Previous studies have highlighted several factors that may influence pre-service teachers' readiness to teach, professional identity, teaching self-efficacy (Ramdani et al., 2021), and ability to use technology in teaching (Tiba & Condy, 2020).

Self-determination has been identified as a critical and important factor in determining the readiness of pre-service teachers' to teach (Hathaway et al., 2023). However, pre-service teachers in early childhood, who are undergoing training, often struggle with self-regulation and require support from faculty mentors as decisions, set goals, and be accountable for their learning and growth, (Guay et al., 2020). High-quality coaching directly and indirectly involves providing opportunities for ECE pre-service teachers to apply their learning in authentic classroom settings. The quality of coaching and instruction provided to pre-service teachers during their training has also been a key determinant of their preparedness to teach (Rauf et al., 2021). Counterproductive use of technology is also a critical factor that can negatively impact pre-service teachers' readiness to teach. Past research has indicated that providing quality examples, gaining experience in class, and feeling motivated and supported during the design process are valuable strategies for improving the digital skills of pre-service teachers and that pre-service teachers may not engage in technology integration activities unless they are compulsory and may not feel comfortable using technology in education even after training (Kulaksız & Toran, 2022).

Self-determination, quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology impact pre-service teachers' readiness. However, there is still a research gap on how these factors interact with each other and influence the development of effective early childhood education professionals (Ye et al., 2024). This study specifically investigates the role of self-determination, quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology as critical factors that may influence their ECE pre-service teachers' readiness to teach.

Research Questions

This study focuses on how self-determination, quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology affect the readiness of ECE pre-service teachers in teaching. This involves ECE pre-service teachers enrolled in a local college of Bukidnon.

Specifically, it seeks answers to the following:

1. What is the participants' level of self-determination?
2. What is the participants' assessment of their teachers' quality of coaching?
3. What is the participants' extent of counterproductive use of technology?
4. What is the participants' level of readiness to teach?
5. Do the participants' self-determination, teachers' quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology significantly influence their readiness to teach?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, which investigate the relationships among variables and determine the degree to which two or more variables are associated with one another. Through this approach, the researcher this design determined the relationship between the variables -self-determination, quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology - and pre-service teachers' readiness to teach. Pre-service teachers from a local college were asked to complete surveys and questionnaires to determine how self-determination, quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology influence their readiness to teach. The study involved 120 4th-year students taking the Bachelor in Early Childhood Education program and were enrolled in their internship course and actively participated in their practicum/pre-service teaching. Additionally, the participants were able to satisfactorily complete all professional education and major courses under the ECE program. The research instrument consisted of modified self-determination scale, quality of coaching scale, counter-productive use of technology scale and pre-service readiness scale. Permits and consent were obtained prior to the administrations of the questionnaires. In analyzing the data, the researchers used Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution to describe the demographic profile of the participants and their responses on the different scales. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to determine the predictive capacity of the independent variables

RESULTS

Based on the data gathered from this study, the following findings are thus presented:

1. Self-determination as a powerful positive predictor of readiness to teach indicated that one of the core aspects of intrinsic motivation and autonomy was a key factor in teachers' preparation.
2. The type of coaching preservice teachers received showed an even more significant positive effect on their readiness, underscoring the importance of mentorship and guidance in teacher development.
3. The relationship between counterproductive technology use and readiness was negatively correlated. However, the lack of significance indicates that its influence is not as strong as some of the other areas explored.
4. A high level of preparedness was indicated by an overall readiness assessment, confirming the performance of current teacher education programs in providing such skills and knowledge to future teachers.
5. ECE Preservice teachers' readiness to teach is a significant influence with a high level of self-determination and effective quality of coaching. However, counterproductive use of technology has a negative effect on readiness, showing that it does not significantly influence readiness to teach.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage and mean showing the respondents' self-determination level. With an overall mean score of 3.98, $SD=0.49$, it indicates that the respondents have a high degree of self-determination. The findings show that the majority of ECE pre-service teachers feel competent, self-assured, and independent in their choices and behavior. The low standard deviation indicates that the responses are closer to the overall mean, showing conformity and a high level of agreement among the respondents. This result is supported by a study which found that teachers' high level of self-determination allows them to perform well and become committed to their profession (Kazanopoulos et al., 2022).

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Preservice Teacher's Self-Determination

Research Question 1. What is the ECE Pre-service teachers' level of self-determination?

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	17	14.17
3.51-4.50	High	85	70.83
2.51-3.50	Moderate	18	15.00

1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.00
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		120	100.0
Overall Mean		3.98	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.49	

Table 2 shows the pre-service teachers' satisfaction level regarding the quality of coaching they received. It shows that the respondents perceived their teachers' coaching quality as exceptionally high, with an overall mean of 4.36, SD = 0.55, described as "High" level. The low overall standard deviation entails that there was an agreement among participants regarding the effectiveness of the coaching they received. This result suggests that pre-service teachers received highly effective quality coaching that helped them in their teaching careers by engaging them in various activities involving classroom management, integrative teachings strategies, lesson planning and assessment practices. This conforms with (Russell et al., 2020) which suggest that high quality of coaching programs develop student skills in teaching, which subsequently improved their overall preparedness in teaching.

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Preservice Teachers Perceived Quality of Coaching

Research Question 2. What is the participants' assessment of their teachers' quality of coaching?

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	54	45.00
3.51-4.50	High	57	47.50
2.51-3.50	Moderate	8	6.67
1.51-2.50	Low	1	0.83
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		120	100.0
Overall Mean		4.36	
Interpretation		High	
SD		0.55	

Table 3 shows the level of the respondents counterproductive use of technology. The overall mean score for counterproductive use of technology was 2.69, with an SD=0.83, indicating a moderate level of counterproductive use of technology. Although there are some aspects where a pre-service teacher may develop a negative habit towards using technology, it does not severely affect their teaching readiness. The low standard deviation indicates low variability, and most respondents' responses are close to the mean. This result is consistent with the study of Duan et al.,(2022) who found that

the counterproductive use of technology does not significantly correlate with the teaching performance of the teachers.

Table 3

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of Preservice Teachers' Counterproductive use of Technology

Research Question 3. What is the participants' extent of counterproductive use of technology?

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	3	2.50
3.51-4.50	High	15	12.50
2.51-3.50	Moderate	53	44.17
1.51-2.50	Low	37	30.83
1.00-1.50	Very Low	12	10.00
	Total	120	100.0
	Overall Mean	2.69	
	Interpretation	Moderate	
	SD	0.83	

Table 4 shows the Preservice Teachers' Level of Readiness to Teach. The result shows a High Level of Readiness to Teach, with an overall mean score of 4.24 and an SD=0.51. The participants' positive agreement and minimal variability regarding their preparedness to teach are indicated by this low standard deviation. According to the outcome, the participants exhibit all the necessary skills and abilities, possesses strong pedagogical knowledge, and confidence in managing the class effectively and to deliver quality instruction that promotes student learning. This result corresponds to the result of the study of (Bhebhe, 2022), which concluded good theoretical foundation in education, mentorship and support, developing competencies and practical teaching experiences helps pre-service teachers to be more confident in in the teaching and learning process.

Table 4

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of ECE Pre-service Teachers Readiness to Teach

Research Question 4. What is the participants' level of readiness to teach?

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	41	34.17
3.51-4.50	High	69	57.50
2.51-3.50	Moderate	8	6.67
1.51-2.50	Low	2	1.67
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00

Total	120	100.0
Overall Mean	4.24	
Interpretation	High	
SD	0.51	

Table 5 presents the regression analysis of the influence of participants' self-determination, teachers' quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology on their readiness to teach. The regression analysis was used after ensuring that the data set met the assumptions of regression. The correlation is strong at .651; the variance inflation factor or VIF ranges from 1.028 to 1.249 which points to the absence of multicollinearity and the histogram and QQ plot are provided in Appendix E. The data reveal that the whole model is significant with $F(3,116) = 28.40, p = .001$. Thus, the null hypothesis that the participants' self-determination, teachers' quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology do not significantly influence their readiness to teach is rejected. Pre-service teachers who are more determined, who have cooperating teachers whose quality of coaching is high and who are not so distracted with the counterproductive use of technology are more ready to teach. It entails that pre-service teachers who exhibit higher levels of self-determination are perceived to be more capable of teaching effectively. Given that strong sense of determination, pre-service teachers are more ready to deliver instruction, manage the classroom and work with their colleagues, if their instructors, and supervising and cooperating teachers serve as good mentors and if they know how to manage their time and available resource, and avoid distractions from technology. On the other hand, the counterproductive use of technology fails to reject the null hypothesis for counterproductive use of technology, suggesting that this factor does not significantly influence readiness to teach within the sample studied. The study of Lancaster (2023), emphasizes that preservice teachers are less engaged to teaching since they are distracted due to social media, and use of digital devices. Here, since preservice teachers have limited exposure to technology, its negative effect is not present.

Research Question 5. Do the participants' self-determination, teachers' quality of coaching, and counterproductive use of technology significantly influence their readiness to teach?

Table 5
Multiple Linear Regression Model on Self-Determination, Teachers' Quality of Coaching, and Counterproductive use of Technology as Predictors of their Readiness to Teach

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.33	.362		3.68	.000
Self Determination	.369	.081	.357	4.53**	.000

Teachers' Quality of Coaching	of 373	.073	.402	5.10**	.000
Counterproductive Use of Technology		-.066	.044	-.109	-1.52 .132
Model Summary					
R = .651 R ² = .423 Adjusted R ² = .409 F(3,116)=28.40** p = .001					

Conclusions

The significant positive influence of self-determination on the readiness to teach ECE preservice teachers affirms the notion of the importance and value of encouraging and cultivating self-determination to strengthen the motivation of preservice teachers. This indicates that professional development programs should focus on improving self-efficacy, emotional intelligence, and perceptions of the future work environment to foster outstanding commitment among preservice teachers. The strong impact of quality coaching on ECE preservice teachers' readiness to teach highlights preservice teachers are likely to evaluate the quality of coaching that they experience and judge if it results in effective teaching or further improvement. When coaching is viewed positively, it increases motivation and promotes a growth mindset, contributing to greater readiness. Although counterproductive use of technology has a negative effect on readiness this implies that when preservice teachers find technology useful for teaching and easy to use, they are more likely to incorporate it positively into their teaching practices, enhancing their readiness. However, when technology is used counterproductively, such as for distraction or procrastination, its adverse effects may not be significant enough to outweigh the positive contributions of self-determination and quality coaching.

The overarching interconnected findings and significant implications emerge for self-determination, quality of coaching, and ECE preservice teachers' readiness to teach. The high rate of overall readiness scores suggests that current teacher education programs, specifically Early Childhood Education of PBCC, are generally successful in preparing future teachers. However, content knowledge and its application to various areas in the curriculum and instruction can still be enhanced.

Recommendations

The findings and conclusions of the study provide actionable recommendations for school administrators, teachers, preservice teachers.

1. School administrators may:
 - 1.1 develop curriculum initiatives that support trainings cum workshops designed to enhance self-determination and promote educational consciousness.
 - 1.2 develop a more structured mentoring program that will motivate students and encourages them to have a sense of autonomy and accountability.
2. ECE teachers may:

2.1 employ teaching strategies that support autonomy, and motivate ECE preservice teachers to prepare for the teaching profession

2.2 provide coaching initiative that creates learning from the experiences of their mentors and promote smart and productive application of technology.

3. Preservice teachers may:

3.1 participate in various programs and activities, including but not limited smart use of technology that hone their skills and values as future teachers

3.2 establish a positive relationship with their mentors and teachers and ask for advice to address various challenges in the profession and to improve their knowledge and skills in teaching

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher upheld strict ethical standards to protect the rights, welfare, and dignity of 4th-year Pre-Service Teachers of Pangantucan Bukidnon Community College (PBCC) Bachelor in Early Childhood Education (BECEd). Informed and voluntary consent was obtained after clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, benefits, and risks. Confidentiality was ensured by anonymizing data and restricting access to authorized personnel. The study prioritized fairness, cultural sensitivity, and participant well-being while minimizing risks. It adhered to the PBCC Research Ethics Guidelines and was approved by the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee (LCREC), ensuring credibility, transparency, and integrity.

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